

Morocco's Geopolitics of Religion in Sub-Saharan Africa Promoting Religious Dialogue and Spiritual Security

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Abstract

The intersection of religion and politics dates back to a long history. Religion plays a fundamental role in shaping states' foreign policies and international relations. Morocco has been one of the major religious references in the Sahel region and West Africa; nevertheless, it tries to spread its sphere of influence in other African regions. The overlap between religion and Rabat's foreign policy has two major interests. First, it tries to foster its geopolitical presence in the African continent, and to introduce Morocco as a moderate religious model to be followed. Second, it tries to approach extremism and terrorism with a soft strategy, since religion has a historical powerful role in motivating people. In this regard, this chapter tries to investigate the use religion as a soft power in strengthening Morocco's foreign policy and promoting its public diplomacy in Sub-Saharan Africa. Also, it discusses Morocco's role in spreading interfaith dialogue and spiritual security through: the establishment of religious institutions, the royal tours in African countries and the royal speeches.

Keywords: Morocco's foreign policy; geopolitics of religion; sub-Saharan Africa; soft power; spiritual security

1. Introduction

Morocco has played geostrategic and geopolitical roles in Africa for many decades starting with military, economic and political support to cultural and religious influences in the continent. Morocco has been perceived as a religious reference; mainly in Sahel region and West Africa, the fact that strengthened Morocco's symbolic position in the region. Accordingly, historical as well as new religious ties have been used to achieve Rabat geopolitical interests, especially to curb the spread of terrorism and save the state's autonomy and security.

Morocco is recognized as a leading country in providing and spreading spiritual security in the African continent. In 2014, many African countries requested Rabat to share with them its experience in religious education of moderate Islam. This agreement intended to enhance security cooperation between Rabat and other African states and open promising horizons in this important area. The cooperation is not limited to one country in the region over others but it includes many parts of the continent, which are invited to achieve safe and secure Africa. The African continent is witnessing dramatic events for many decades that have led to violence, human trafficking, poverty and famine; thus, this experience used to be approached from a purely military vision that aimed to curb the spread of violence and chaos. However, after the replication of those experiences and the spread of global violence it was obvious that the military approach is not the only solution for this problem, pointing out that religion and culture play a prominent role in promoting dialogue between nations and civilizations and then decreasing the spread of extremism and terrorism.

This renewed religious cooperation under the leadership of Morocco; including the training of Imams *Morshidin* and *Morshidat*¹, the Institute of *African Ulema*², the reconstruction of religious places in African countries, and the

supervision on Sufi trends and *Zawaya*³, has contributed in the development of the region and has shown effective results in preventing extremism. Nevertheless, Morocco did not stop at that level, but was keen to talk about the problems of terrorism and extremism on many national and international occasions. Morocco also stressed the values of tolerance, brotherhood and communication between cultures, civilizations and religions. This approach led to the politicization of culture and religion by virtue of the overlap that the fields of studies are witnessing.

This chapter reviews Morocco's religious policy towards Africa, starting from a general overview of Morocco's Africa foreign policy to the spread of interfaith dialogue and spiritual security in the continent. The paper argues that Morocco's new vision towards the continent is based on a leading, but in the same time cooperative, policy that seeks to use a soft strategy to handle the problems of terrorism and extremism. This strategy goes hand in hand with Rabat's geopolitical interests in the region which aims to increase its religious presence and influence.

2. The Geopolitics of Religion in International Relations and Foreign Policy: *Defining the Term*

Geopolitics is a complex term that has no unified or unique definition⁴, nevertheless, it can be, practically, defined as “the science of study of the relation between geography, power and politics and the transactions resulted from their combination”⁵. Additionally, the use of the word geopolitics means to “emphasise the particular significance of a space in order to, for example, identify political actors, formulate political goals, or analyse the tools that are available for the implementation of politics”⁶. From these definitions we can assume that geopolitical sciences studies the intersection of political activities, power (in all its forms) and geography, and how space can play a significant role in determining world's politics in general and regional politics in particular.

However, space in geopolitics does not mean only geographical territories but also “immaterial spaces such as cultural, religious, or virtual spaces”⁷.

Since the term geopolitics is complex in nature; then, its intersection with religion becomes more complex and controversial. Religion in its nature is “the ultimate denial of the significance of earthly distinctions”, while geopolitics is “a way to wield or explain power by making territorial (geographical) distinctions”⁸. Religion is the relationship between human beings and God, it is “a set of beliefs and practices relating to the gods worshipped by a given group of people and handed down through tradition”⁹. Hence, at first glance, it seems that there is no close relationship between religion, or religious practices, and politics, but in the contrary, religion is one of the fundamental factors that shape international relations, international politics of states’ foreign policies.

Throughout history, it has been proved that religion “has a central force that motivates and mobilizes people” and can lead to conflict and peace simultaneously¹⁰. Religious teachings have been misleadingly used as arguments to justify political practices such as the Crusades and what is called ‘Islamic Jihad’¹¹. In those cases religion had a political purpose, since it was the strongest argument to invade or start war especially that it was justified by the doctrine of *divine right of kings*¹² which was widespread in Europe for any centuries¹³. However, even after the spread of the secularization theory after the Peace of Westphalia agreements in 1648, religion has regained its impact and powerful role in international relations especially in the second half of the 20th century¹⁴.

The power of religion has two folds; it can be used to spread clashes and conflicts and promote proxy wars in many regions around the world; on the other hand, it can be used to spread mutual understanding and spiritual security. Recently, and due to globalization process and the spread of technology and communication, religion is omnipresent in every communicative situation or

practice; either formal or informal. Hence, religion as a soft power means to get what you want without the use of hard power, coercion or payments¹⁵. World states are well aware of the role religion can play as a soft power to promote their political practices softly and gain more followers and more political and economic profits. Accordingly, religion and geopolitics are fused in recent studies to deeply analyse the intersection of religion and politics.

The term geopolitics of religion has become well known in the analysis of recent political topics. The geopolitics of religion analyses the way in which religion can affect political activities within a territory or geographical space in order to serve political objectives¹⁶. Moreover, geopolitics of religion “focuses on analyses of a political actor and its actions and geopolitical goals”, while geopolitics of religions (in plural) focuses more on analyses of the similarities and differences between religions¹⁷. The geopolitics of religion is the coalition of religion and politics which crosses the geographical borders of states to achieve their national interests¹⁸. The states purposes and interests are dynamic and subject to change. For instance, decades ago European states were interested in conquering colonial territories to expense their royal realm and secure their crowns, while nowadays states are interested in four common purposes namely security, autonomy, welfare and status and prestige¹⁹. Moreover, the state’s foreign policy objectives are expressed through its policy orientations in four conditions as adopted by Holsti²⁰. First, the structure of international system in which the state is involved, second, the nature of the state’s domestic attitudes and its social and economic needs, third, the external threat to the state’s internal values and interests, and finally, geographical location to which the state belong. Generally speaking, states’ foreign policies are determined by their internal needs that cannot be achieved without external help, and different tools are used to achieve them among which we find religion. In this regard, religion is chosen by policy-makers and foreign policy officials to gain the state’s interests across

borders, to protect its autonomy, to enhance security and to save its status and prestige.

Religion as soft power is also used as a solution to fight extremism and curb the spread of transnational terrorism. Since religion can strongly motivate people to follow the instructions and obey the laws, religion has become politicised to convince people to follow beliefs and ideas. Hence, religious leaders are viewed also as geopoliticians in international relations²¹. Many states around the world are using religion as a soft power to spread their sphere of influence especially in their geopolitical regions. Islam; for instance, is one of the most influential religions in the world, and two major countries compete to spread their spiritual presence in the world; namely, Iran and Saudi Arabia²². Nevertheless, Morocco is also playing a significant Islamic leading role in the African continent.

Moroccan foreign policy toward Africa; for instance, aims at strengthening internal autonomy and political stabilization through external diplomatic relations with a range of African nations. In addition to its strategies of economic diversification, Morocco is working to enhance its internal security, to promote its national prestige, as well as to establish cultural and religious diplomacies in the African region, and religion is a key factor to enhance its foreign policy with Western Africa.

3. Religion in Morocco's Foreign Policy towards Sub-Saharan Africa

3.1. Morocco's Africa Foreign Policy: *An Historical Perspective*

Morocco's African foreign policy is by no means a new phenomenon; rather it is rooted in history for many decades as it is determined by its strategic geopolitical pertinence. However, Morocco's foreign policy in the continent is influenced by many factors that could be reviewed in political, economic, security, cultural and religious dimensions^{23 24}.

Morocco had a very prominent military and logistical role in the independence of a range of African States during the European colonisation. Accordingly, in 1960 Morocco trained more than 2000 African fighters from Angola, Mozambique, Guinea-Bissau and the republic of Cape Verde²⁵. In 1977 and 1978, Morocco had supported Zaire²⁶ by sending military troops in order to sustain the Mobutu²⁷ regime²⁸. Additionally, Morocco was a founding member of the African Unity in 1963²⁹, and even after the withdrawal of King Hassan II from the organization, Morocco was always diplomatically present in international summits and forums that tackle issues related to the African region³⁰. In addition, “at the non-governmental level, Moroccan universities have been hosting students from other African states since the mid-1980s, which has created solid personal and social links between Moroccans and people from those other states”³¹. All these dimensions have enriched Morocco's Sub-Saharan African intercultural and interfaith communication, as we Morocco's prestigious position in the Continent.

At the cultural level, Abdeljaouad Sekkat maintains that “history witnesses the leading role of Morocco in the cultural movement in the African countries, and its influence in their development for millennia. Similarly, the present witnesses the extension of this role”³². In other words, intercultural communication in Morocco's African relations is rooted in history and represented in their civilizations. In the same sense, Sekkat adds:

it is recognized that this cultural communication between the two sides was not born late, rather its roots are extended in the depths of history; noting that Morocco's African relations date back to a long time [...], as well as the cultural intermixture that existed between the two parties in that era [...]³³

Going back in history, a great credit for the entry of Islam and its spread in large areas of West Africa or Western Sudan such as Ghana, Senegal, Mali and others, is due to the role of Almoravid dynasty³⁴, which worked on expanding in these

areas and spreading Islam in its Maliki Doctrine and settling preachers among its tribes³⁵; ³⁶; ³⁷. Since that time Morocco was playing the leading role of an Islamic sovereignty in those African regions, and it has undertaken a series of scientific missions to West Africa, mainly West Sudanian Savanna in order to teach Quran and Hadith under the supervision of renowned Imams and mentors³⁸.

In this regard, the acts of intercultural communication and acculturation were determined by the friction and cross-fertilization of cultures. Moroccan culture has become prominent in a range of African religious rituals such as the Moroccan way of reading the Quran, and the Moroccan way of drawing the Ottoman line etc.³⁹. In the same vein, Moroccan Tijaniyya, EL-Qadiriyya and Shadhili Sufi trends have been adopted by Sub-Saharan African countries such as Senegal, Sudan and Comoros⁴⁰; ⁴¹.

Furthermore, some Sub-Saharan African countries' mosques are built in the Moroccan style such as in Mali, Senegal, Chad, Ivory Coast and Guinea Bissau. In this context, the connotations of some African mosques' architecture and names show the deep religious and cultural representation of Morocco in these countries. For instance, the Moroccan Mosque in Mauritania, Hassan II Mosque in Gabon, Fes Mosque in Comoros, and Mohammed VI Mosque in Tanzania highlight the strong symbolic representation of Morocco in Sub-Saharan Africa⁴²; ⁴³. Thus, Sorrells maintains:

When you go to places of worship, such as synagogue, church, mosque, or temple, there are particular architectural features, artifacts, uses of space, and language, as well as verbal and nonverbal practices that construct the cultural space of these particular places. These are all cultural spaces that are constructed through the communicative practices developed and lived by people in particular places.⁴⁴

The construction of cultural spaces strongly affects the relationship between the cultural space and the culture in which space was constructed. Hence, the Moroccan culture has been displaced and replaced in Sub-Saharan African countries, the fact that shifted the interests of Morocco's foreign policy towards Africa. More critically, Morocco has played a symbolic role as a religious reference for most Western African countries since the majority of Sufi trends are associated with Morocco. Thus, Morocco frequently uses religion in its public diplomacy towards West Africa.

3.1.1. Cultural and Religious Diplomacies in Morocco's African Foreign Policy 311

In the same line with the south-south strategy proposed by Morocco⁴⁵, or as it is also viewed as win-win strategy⁴⁶, and which focuses on enhancing the African continent and creating new opportunities at the economic and political levels, cultural and religious diplomacies have taken a very important part in this strategy. The Moroccan successive visits to a range of Sub-Saharan African countries, such as Rwanda, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Senegal, Zambia etc.⁴⁷, have shown the Kingdom's intention to set the ground for healthy and strong relationships with sub-Saharan African countries at all levels, which include cultural and religious ties. However, this is evident through the royal donations of thousands of Holy Quran copies, which are printed by *Mohammed VI's Foundation for the Publication of Holy Quran*, the religious meetings with Imams and *Zawiyas'* followers in many African countries and the royal leadership of Friday Prayers in many African cities⁴⁸.

The pressing need of promoting dialogue among cultures is highly viewed in Morocco's cultural and religious diplomacy towards Africa. Thus, several cultural and religious events are organized under the patronage of King Mohammed VI in which the presence of African culture, art and traditions are

strongly viewed in many Moroccan cultural projects. Some of these cultural events are; the Folklore Music Festival⁴⁹, the International Film Festival of Marrakech⁵⁰, Festival Mawazin: Rhythms of The World⁵¹, Tangier International Music Festival⁵², The Festival of Meknés Volubilis⁵³, The International Art Fair in Casablanca⁵⁴, The Spirit of Fez Foundation, and The International Festival of African Fashion⁵⁵, which took place in Dakhla in 2018 in its 11th edition.

Morocco's cultural diplomacy towards Africa seeks to open a dialogue between cultures and civilisations by bringing artists and participants from different cultural backgrounds to collaborate and produce new meaning of intercultural-interfaith communication. This strategy aims also to affirm the central role of intercultural dialogue as an effective instrument of understanding between peoples and a means by which conflicts could be resolved. Hence, Morocco is regarded as one of the most culturally active countries in North Africa combining its national cultural-religious diversity and its openness to other African cultures and religions.

Moreover, King Mohammed VI stresses the importance of promoting intercultural-interfaith dialogue in his speeches claiming that the world nowadays urgently needs awareness campaigns of the crucial role of effective intercultural-interfaith communication so as to be able to face all kinds of intercultural conflict that lead to terrorism and extremism.

3.2. Religion as a Soft Factor to Promote Spiritual Security in the African Continent

Due to the increase of terrorism and extremism in the globe, intercultural-interfaith dialogue has become a need. Despite the rise of globalization and transportation and the openness to other cultures, conflicts between peoples and nations in the 21st century are argued to be cultural and religious in the first place⁵⁶. For instance, the terrorist operations the world witnessed in recent years,

reinforced hostility and marginalization towards some cultures and religions because they were approached from a religious perspective⁵⁷. However, although the whole world has witnessed such terrorist attacks, the most affected regions are the African continent and Middle East⁵⁸.

However, following the demonstrations, political divisions and military coups of many African countries, it was easy to spread terrorism and extremism. Fragile States in Africa are today places where poverty is mostly severe, the thing that led to the spread of weapons-smuggling, corruption, illegal trade and trafficking in human beings. More critically, these unstable regions have become breeding grounds for organised crime and terrorism which threaten many African regions; mainly, Nigeria, Mali, Senegal, Libya, Guinea-Bissau⁵⁹.

Such unstable states offer space to train and recruit dissatisfied followers using ideological and xenophobic discourses to spread hostility hatred and revenge. Hence, the growth of radical extremism in sub-Saharan Africa necessitated rapid action by neighbouring countries and international organisations to curb the spread of this phenomenon. In this regard, international organisations, alliances and conferences arise to find practical solutions to stop the incursion of terrorism.

Morocco is regarded as an active agent in the African continent since it is untiringly working towards the promotion of peace, stability and co-existence. After the tragedy of Casablanca in May 2003 which led to the death of 47 people, Morocco realized the need to protect the Islamic religion from distortion and deviation in order to stop the threat of such dramatic events. A proactive management of the religious field was required and urgent solutions were necessitated for the fight against terrorism. The first step towards this mission was to modify the kingdom's constitution, thus, among the fundamental modifications was "He [the king] presides over the Superior Council of the

Ulema, charged with the study of questions that He submits to it” when the superior council is “the sole instance enabled to comment on the religious consultations (Fatwas) before being officially agreed to, on the questions to which it has been referred and this, on the basis of the tolerant principles, precepts and designs of Islam” in order to control the kingdom’s religious sphere⁶⁰.

In this sense, religion in Morocco’s foreign policy has been chosen as an alternative tool to achieve many interests, among which the most prominent are; first, to enhance internal security, which is closely related to external stability, and second, to spread Morocco’s sphere of religious influence in the continent; especially West Africa. In other words, Morocco is using its historical religious ties with many African countries to expand its spiritual presence, and promote its public diplomacy and make it more attractive⁶¹.

3.3. The Symbolism of The Commandership of the Faithful in Morocco’s Sub-Saharan Foreign Policy

King Mohammed VI represents the commander of the faithful in Morocco, which has a strong spiritual authority in the kingdom. The Commandership of the Faithful is a neutral and impartial institution which; headed by HM King Mohammed VI, plays a fundamental role in preserving the rights and freedom of believers in Morocco and protecting the state’s religion “Islam”

Not surprisingly, the symbolic representation of the Commandership of the Faithful is historically rooted in Morocco’s African religious relations. The Moroccan sovereign was always recognised as Amir El-Mouminin (Commander of the Faithful) because of Morocco’s role in spreading Islam in West Africa and Sahel regions, the fact that strengthened Morocco’s African religious relations⁶². For instance, in Timbuktu, Friday prayers and its Khutba (sermon) were delivered in the name of Amir El Mouminin (King of Morocco).

From this point of view, Mohamed Chtatou stated that “Interestingly enough, his religious status is, even, recognized in many countries in West Africa, that acknowledge his religious title of ‘Commander of the Faithful,’ especially among the Tidjane communities in the Western parts of the continent.”⁶³. Furthermore, Morocco is recognized as a religious reference and one of the most stable places in the African continent, hence, the Moroccan model of Moderate Islam was needed in several African countries in order to fight terrorism. Morocco; nowadays, is promoting its religious soft power which is led by “Imarate Al Muminin” (commander of the faithful) or even *the commander of the African faithful*.

The keenness of the King of Morocco, as the Commander of the Faithful, to employ his religious and spiritual symbolism for the inhabitants of the countries of the Sahel and West Africa, has positively affected security and stability in the region⁶⁴, as well as it has enhanced Morocco’s religious geopolitical position in Africa. Additionally, preserving the influence of Moroccan religious privacy that is characterized by moderation has been helping in promoting spiritual security in the continent, by taking the Moroccan experience in managing religious affairs as a successful model for spiritual security and combating terrorism.

3.4. Morocco’s Promotion of Moderate Islam in Africa

Morocco, recently, is playing a leading role in religious affairs by promoting new strategy of tolerant Islam in Africa. The religious diplomacy has become one of the most important domains in Morocco’s foreign policy, especially during the increase of Jihadist movements in Africa and Middle East⁶⁵. Within the framework of its soft religious and cultural diplomacies, Morocco has launched several initiative contributions in the African continent so as to export its experience in Spiritual Security⁶⁶ and Intercultural-Interfaith dialogue.

Hence, ambitious practical responses were proposed by HM King Mohammed VI to prevent the spread of extremism. The King established the Mohammed VI Institute of Morchidins and Morchidates, which is an academy for the training of Imams that was inaugurated on 27 March 2015. However, the main aim of the institution is to spread moderate Islam in the African region based on Maliki School, Ash'ari theology and d Sunni Sufism⁶⁷. Respectively, El Merini stated that “due to the intensive initiatives to build Imams in accordance with the principles of a moderate and tolerant Islam, Morocco is about to become one of the most influential spiritual centres in the Muslim world”⁶⁸. This institution is hosting students from different African countries; mainly, Northern and Western African countries⁶⁹ and those imams are going to be able to learn “values of moderate Islam, tolerance, intercultural dialogue and respect between religions”⁷⁰.

In the same vein, Mohammed VI Foundation of African Ulema in Fes was established for the same purposes. Thus, the foundation aims to spread and unify the Moroccan way of teaching moderate Islam in all over the continent. By the time of its inauguration, the foundation included 123 Ulema; 103 from several African countries and 20 from Morocco, however, after two years the number of Ulema has exceeded 330. The institution has its branches in 32 African countries including all African regions, the fact that reflects the African awareness of the prominent role that soft religious strategy plays in the African context. Not surprisingly, the member states that mostly join the foundation are those that are affected by terrorist movements; mainly Sahel region and West and East Africa including; Nigeria, Ethiopia, Mali, Central Africa, Tanzania etc.

The promotion of moderate Islam reveals the intensive initiatives of Morocco in the African environment and the new strategies that it is building so as to foster its foreign policy. Likewise, Sekkat stated:

these and other elements [the cultural and religious diplomacies] are part of the system of the prominent role played by Morocco in favour of Sub-Saharan Africa, and the importance that it attaches to this promising region in various fields and levels, from which the most prominent are the religious dimension and cultural diffusion [...]⁷¹

Apparently, Morocco's promotion of moderate Islam is another soft powerful tool to strengthen its geopolitical position in Africa as well as to protect its territories from transnational terrorism.

3.5. The Politicisation of Religion in Morocco's Foreign Policy: *Religious Discourse as Soft Power*

The promotion of interfaith discourse and spiritual security does not only cover the foundation of institutions, but it is also strongly presented in the King's political discourses. In national and international occasions, events and summits, King Mohammed VI discussed topics related to tolerance, coexistence, interfaith discourse etc. to emphasise the role of spiritual security in preventing terrorism and extremism in the continent. This goes back to the importance of political discourses in influencing and persuading people without the use of hard power.

3.5.1. The Politicisation of Religious Discourse

Globalization has catapulted people from different cultural backgrounds to interact either in real or virtual spaces, however, this interaction has two contradictory facets; it can be done effectively by accepting each other's cultural properties, as it can lead to misunderstandings and conflict. In this sense, stereotypes and prejudices are bound to occur. Although intercultural communication and cultural awareness are crossing borders immensely, stereotypes are similarly growing. Thence, the world is witnessing the rise of terrorism, extremism and ideological discourses that affect world security system. Extremist people are justifying their terrorist acts under the pretext of

religion, discrimination and race issues. Therefore, “cultural issues are been politicised, and are been used for political debates although they actually belong to a completely different era.”⁷²

As a matter of fact, modern political studies are shedding light on the prominence of intercultural discourse in international relations and foreign policy in order to face all kinds of terrorism and cultural clashes that are influencing international peace and security. Therefore, Soyal maintains “culture has become the dominant frame for political issues and policies such as citizenship, security, the economy and so forth”⁷³. This stresses the fact that the promotion and politicization of intercultural dialogue is of paramount interest for maintaining global peace and security. In the African continent, Morocco is playing a fundamental role in manipulating cultural issues such as religious extremism and intercultural clashes.

The main aim of discussing cultural and religious topics in Morocco’s political speeches is to; first, state the kingdom’s achievements in this area, to show its commitment to spread spiritual security in the continent, and to recommend collective actions and shared responsibility towards the continental religious harmony and spiritual security.

3.5.2. Interfaith-Intercultural Discourse as Soft Strategy in Morocco’s Foreign Policy

Political discourses are historically recognized as an ideological set of words that function to persuade the public; usually using coercive power. Nonetheless, political discourses nowadays are using more sophisticated words and soft discursive strategies. The promotion of intercultural and interfaith discourses in King Mohammed VI speeches could be recognized as a soft powerful strategy which is used to influence public opinions and political decisions without the use of coercive power. In this sense, soft power is defined as “the ability to

shape the preferences of others, without the use of force, coercion or violence”⁷⁴. Therefore, it is the ability to influence public opinion and make others behave in a particular way voluntarily.

Nye argued that soft power is not only about influencing people since the influence can rest on coercion, but it is also about attraction which leads to “acquiescence”⁷⁵. Morocco’s new vision of foreign policy is by all odds a soft powerful strategy which managed to guide the African political opinions towards Morocco and attract them to follow its model. Thus, Morocco is using a collaborative strategy which is based on agreements, reconciliation and compromise instead of competitive one which is based on conflict and disagreement

The increase of promoting intercultural-interfaith discourse in Moroccan political speeches in international events is determined by many factors. First, the diversified nature of Moroccan culture as shaped by the convergence of Arab, Amazigh and Saharan-Hassani cultural properties, as well as the religious variety, which stresses the Jewish Muslim historical coexistence. Second, the geopolitical position of Morocco as a link between Africa and Europe and the role it played as a historical commercial bridge through which acculturation and intercultural communication were bound to occur. Third, the prominent role that is played by Morocco as an agent in many international organizations that are concerned with issues of intercultural communication, immigration and interfaith clashes from which we can count the United Nations, the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation, Alliance of Civilizations, the League of Arab States and the Tripartite Forum for Interreligious cooperation for Peace. Forth, Morocco is promoting spiritual security and religious awareness to prevent the Moroccan kingdom from all kinds of terrorism and extremism. Morocco is untiringly working towards the promotion of peace, stability and development in the African Continent. This promotion is explicitly viewed in its humanistic projects

towards African migrants, the promotion of moderate Islam, and the promotion of intercultural-interfaith discourse.

In order to combat rumours about Islam and correct the constructed fallacies about it, Morocco's political speeches are used to represent Islam as a religion based on "Middle Path" teachings and a safety valve against the threat of radicalism and terrorism, especially that media reinforces xenophobic discourses. Moreover, Morocco is situated in Africa, and in order to prevent its national and territorial security from outside and inside attacks, it was necessary to treat this phenomenon with a multidimensional approach. Consequently, Morocco is betting on religious diplomacy in order to create soft solutions for these crises⁷⁶, which can be clearly viewed in the royal discourses.

For instance, in the speech delivered at the inauguration ceremony of Malian president Ibrahim Boubacar Keita in Bamako in September 2013, the King discussed the issue of Islam and the main similarities between Mali and Morocco in religious practices, and he expressed Morocco's support for Malian government in different sectors to combat terrorism and prevent extremism. The Sahel, including Mali, Nigeria, Chad and other countries, is a region where you can find Jihadist and militant groups. Poverty, ethnic conflicts and poor-governance are the fundamental causes behind the rise of terrorist movements. Accordingly, 400,000 Malians were forced to flee their homes between 2012 and 2013 and more than 18 million people in the Sahel region were affected by food crises⁷⁷.

The spread of terrorism threatened the continent security and contributed to the spread of fallacies and misconceptions related to Islam. Hence, the King stressed the role of religious and cultural dimensions to reconstruct spiritually secure and safe Africa. Thus, in the same speech, King Mohammed VI expressed the willingness of Morocco to provide training in the religious sphere for 500

Malian Imams which is mainly devoted to the study of the Maliki rite and of the moral doctrine that rejects any form of hostility and extremism. Moreover, Morocco's commitment towards Mali included also the reconstruction of Mali worship places, the rehabilitation of mausoleums and preservation of manuscripts.

The royal discourses were addressed to high profile politicians to share the action and responsibility towards the African continent in order to combat all kinds of terrorism and organized attacks. Hence, it was mentioned by King Mohammed VI that the military strategies are not enough to stop the spread of xenophobic discourses. In this regard, in the second edition of the International Conference on Intercultural and Interfaith Dialogue held in September 2018 in Fez and represented by Mustapha Ramid, the royal speech highlighted the need for shared responsibility and united action to curb violent extremism:

To be effective, our joint action should be sustainable, comprehensive and flexible to suit changing environments. [...], only a collective resolve capitalizing on the efforts of government, civil society, the media, academics and citizens can tackle reclusiveness and intellectual extremism. Inter-faith, intercultural dialogue is not an abstract concept or a form of intellectual luxury. Determination - on its own - is not enough in this domain. In fact, dialogue is born out of deeply held convictions which require strong commitment, hard work and matching words with action. (Ramid, the International Conference on Intercultural and Interfaith Dialogue, 2018)

The topic of extremism and terrorism is a transnational problem that goes beyond the boundaries of countries to threaten the whole humanity; therefore, all countries including all the components of each country should share the responsibility to demystify and clarify the meaning of Islam to detach it from negative interpretations.

4. Conclusion

In nutshell, religion is one of the main tools in Morocco's foreign policy towards Africa and a key factor in understanding Rabat's role and interests in the region. Religion is an effective and attractive soft power used by geopoliticians to spread their spiritual influence abroad, and Morocco is betting on it to achieve its national and continental goals.

The religious diplomacy pursued by Morocco in the African continent is a major reason for the consolidation of Morocco's foreign relations with the countries of sub-Saharan Africa. Morocco has become a model to be followed in combating all forms of terrorism and extremism, whether on the security level or on the spiritual level. This has made Morocco at the centre of the attention of African countries seeking to solve their internal problems related to the spread of violence, corruption and extremism. Morocco has also been an important religious reference for decades, and its historical relations with African countries have reinforced the role Morocco plays in the region. We cannot separate Rabat's determination to protect its internal security and its persistent and resolute role in combating terrorism at the continental level, since what the world knows today goes beyond separating the country's internal and external challenges.

Even more than that, the Kingdom's endeavour to spread the values of dialogue between cultures and civilizations is closely linked to the royal vision of making Africa at the centre of Morocco's interest and the core of Morocco's foreign policy. From it, we can say that there is a dialectical relationship between the country's public policy and its cultural and religious diplomacies.

Endnotes

[1] Morshidin and Morshidat: male and female religious guides who are responsible of giving; lessons in various Islamic sciences, lessons of preaching and guidance and contribute to the continuous training of religious leaders.

[2] Ulema: Muslim scholars trained in Islam and Islamic law and who can interpret Islam's sciences and doctrines and laws.

[3] Zawaya is the plural of Zawiya which is an Islamic institution associated with Sufis and Sufism in the Islamic World. In Morocco there are many Zawaya like the Qadiriyya and Tijaniyya which are also widely known in Sub-Saharan Africa.

[4] Tabar, M. M. (2022). Geopolitics and the Roots of Islamic Fundamentalism (Case Study: Fundamentalist Groups in the Horn of Africa). *Geopolitics Quarterly Scopus*, 53-74.

[5] Ibid p.55

[6] Mazurkiewicz, P. (2021). Geopolitics and religion. Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw, p. 349

[7] ibid

[8] Dijkink, G. (2006). *When Geopolitics and Religion Fuse: A Historical Perspective*. Routledge: Taylor & Francis Group, p. 192

[9] Mazurkiewicz, P. (2021). Geopolitics and religion. Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw, pp. 351-354

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